

e-ISSN: 2584-1319

Volume 04 Issue 01
Jan-Jun 2026

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Submission Date: Nov
20, 2025

Copyright Received
Date: Dec 12, 2025

A Comprehensive Review on Hydrogel Based Topical Drug Delivery System

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ABSTRACT

Large volumes of biological fluids can be absorbed by hydrogels, which are three-dimensional, insoluble polymer networks. They can be formed through chemical (covalent) or physical (secondary force) cross-linking and may be derived from natural or synthetic polymers. Their key features—swelling ability, mechanical strength, and biocompatibility—greatly influence their performance. They are commonly used in wound dressings, tissue engineering, contact lenses and drug delivery systems because hydrogels contain a large amount of water and closely resemble natural tissue. They can also be designed to respond to environmental stimuli such as temperature or pH, making them highly versatile materials in biomedical applications.

Keywords:-*Hydrogel, drug delivery, stratum corneum, transdermal medication, Polymeric hydrogel, Crosslinking, Swelling behavior*

INTRODUCTION

Wichterle and Lim created poly(2-hydroxethylmethacrylate) (PHEMA) in 1960 and used it in the contact lens industry, demonstrating the modern hydrogel's capacity to absorb moisture while preserving its network structure. This was the first hydrogel ever recorded. Hydrogels have a propensity to absorb large volumes of water inside their interstices and continue to bond it because of their unique three-dimensional crosslinked polymer mesh structure. Also, it preserve the network structure in the swelled state[1].

Hydrogels display these properties because their polymer networks contain polar, water-attracting groups—such as SO_3H , OH , NH_2 , COOH , and CONH_2 —attached as side branches. The swelling character of hydrogels, which is determined by the hydrophilicity of attached groups, swelling media, and crosslinked bonding strength, is responsible for the tendency of water absorption. In addition to regulating water absorption, crosslinking aids in preserving the network's integrity during swelling. In addition to hydrophilic groups' involvement in water uptake[2], crosslinkers are crucial for secondary interactions with biological tissues. Hydrogels are essential in biological applications because of their unique characteristics, which include biodegradability, biocompatibility, hydrophilicity, super absorbency, viscoelasticity, softness, and fluness.

Because of their mucoadhesive and bioadhesive properties, many hydrogels have the capacity to extend the duration of drug residence, making them ideal candidates for use as drug carriers. Hydrogels' semi-solid phase and intrinsic flexibility have recently drawn a lot of attention for energy storage and conversion applications. Conventional

energy conversion and storage devices are unsustainable, hefty and mechanically inflexible[3]. Most commercial devices rely on liquid electrolytes, which pose issues such as leakage, high cost, and potential harm to users. Consequently, hydrogel electrolytes are now being adopted.

They are low-cost, environmentally friendly, biocompatible, biodegradable and semi-solid—properties that make them especially suitable for practical energy-storage applications, including flexible supercapacitors. Hydrogels are used in electrochemical devices to make them elastic, flexible, and able to withstand bending, twisting, folding, and stretching[4]. Compared to conventional electrochemical devices, these features are extremely detrimental. Hydrogels also have the ability to heal themselves, which is essential for wearable and portable electronics. The gadgets' capacity to self-heal or manage damage makes them perfect for lightweight, intelligent electronics.

The basic ideas of the materials utilized in hydrogels, including natural and synthetic polymers, synthesis methods, and varieties of hydrogels based on cross-linking techniques, have all been thoroughly examined in this review. Furthermore, hydrogels' mechanical strength, biocompatibility, biodegradability, and swellability have all been demonstrated using current hydrogels, covering everything from the fundamentals to the most recent ideas. In summary, the discussion covered hydrogels used as electrolytes, their mechanical and self-healing properties and their applications in both electrochemical and medical devices.[5]

TYPES OF GELS**Hydrogels**

A hydrogel is a soft material made from

crosslinked hydrophilic polymers that can swell in water-based solutions and hold large amounts of water. It can be molded into various shapes and its properties can be altered in response to external stimuli, making it useful in various applications such as drug delivery and tissue engineering [6]. They may transport hydrophilic but not hydrophobic drugs and have a reduced capacity to permeate the epidermal barrier [7, 8].

Organogel

Low molecular weight chemicals aggregate in organic mediums to produce three-dimensional fibrous structures that tangle without crystallization, giving rise to the soft material known as organogel[9] These materials can be created by integrating functional chromophores into gel networks, and they may find use in optoelectronic devices. Depending on the needed qualities, they can be made from synthetic polymers like polyvinyl alcohol, polyacrylamide, and polyethylene glycol or natural polymers like gelatin, alginate, and chitosan.

Hydrogels are generally classified into two types: physical hydrogels, which are held together by weak interactions such as hydrogen bonding, ionic attractions, or van der Waals forces; and chemical hydrogels, which are strengthened through covalent cross-links. Their swelling behavior, mechanical strength, and biocompatibility are crucial factors influencing their structure and performance. Hydrogels closely resemble the extracellular matrix (ECM) due to their soft and flexible nature, making them ideal for biomedical applications.

Drug delivery systems, wound dressings, tissue engineering, contact lenses, biosensors, and cell encapsulation are just a few of the many applications for them. Hydrogels can also be stimuli-responsive, meaning they undergo changes in structure

or properties in response to external factors like pH, temperature, light, or ionic strength. This smart behavior makes them suitable for controlled or targeted drug delivery.

They are useful in regenerative medicine because of their high water content and porous structure, which facilitate cellular development and nutrition delivery. All things considered, hydrogels are adaptable substances that show great promise in contemporary pharmacological and biological domains by bridging the gap between synthetic materials and natural tissues. In addition to being simple to create, organogels' lipophilicity allows them to breakdown hydrophobic drugs and enhance their absorption across the epidermal barrier. The major drawback of organogels is their oily nature, which sticks to the skin and leaves greasy residues, making them difficult to remove. This ultimately reduces patient compliance. [10]

NOVEL APPROACH OF HYDROGELS

The novel approach of hydrogels focuses on enhancing their functionality, responsiveness and biocompatibility for advanced biomedical and pharmaceutical applications. Traditional hydrogels are limited by poor mechanical strength and uncontrolled drug release, but modern hydrogel designs overcome these challenges through innovative strategies[11]. Novel hydrogels with enhanced functionality, reactivity, and application potential have been developed as a result of recent developments in hydrogel technology. The drawbacks of traditional hydrogels, such as their weak mechanical strength, restricted responsiveness, and uncontrollable drug release, are intended to be addressed by these new-generation hydrogels. One major innovation is the creation of stimuli-responsive or “smart” hydrogels, which

can alter their physical or chemical properties in response to external stimuli like temperature, pH, light, magnetic field, enzymes, or ionic strength. Such hydrogels allow for controlled and site-specific drug delivery, releasing therapeutic agents only under specific physiological conditions. By combining the benefits of polymer networks and nanoparticles, nanocomposite hydrogels enhance mechanical stability, swelling characteristics, and bioactivity. Adding components like graphene oxide, silica, or metal nanoparticles improves the hydrogel's mechanical strength and provides additional functions, such as antimicrobial properties and imaging capabilities. Self-healing hydrogels are capable of repairing their structure after mechanical damage due to reversible bonds like hydrogen or ionic interactions.

This feature greatly improves their durability and lifespan in biomedical settings. Biodegradable and bioadhesive hydrogels have been developed to ensure safe degradation and better adhesion to biological tissues, enhancing their use in drug delivery and surgical applications. Furthermore, 3D-printed hydrogels have made it possible to precisely build scaffolds that resemble the architecture of real tissues, opening up new possibilities in tissue engineering and regenerative medicine. Overall, these novel approaches have transformed hydrogels into multifunctional, intelligent materials with applications in personalized medicine, biosensing, wound care, and regenerative therapies. By integrating smart polymers, nanotechnology, and bioengineering, the next generation of hydrogels holds tremendous potential to revolutionize biomedical and pharmaceutical research. Recent advancements include the development of stimuli-responsive or "smart" hydrogels that respond to temperature, pH, light, enzymes, or ionic strength, allowing controlled and site-

specific drug release. Nanocomposite hydrogels, formed by incorporating nanoparticles, nanofibers, or liposomes, show improved mechanical stability, conductivity, and bioactivity[12]. Injectable and self-healing hydrogels represent another novel approach, enabling minimally invasive administration and rapid recovery of deformation. Biodegradable and bioadhesive hydrogels are designed to degrade safely within the body and adhere strongly to biological tissues, improving therapeutic outcomes[13].

ADVANTAGES OF HYDROGELS [14-19]:

High Water Content: Hydrogels can absorb and retain large amounts of water, keeping tissues hydrated.

Biocompatibility: They are generally non-toxic and well-tolerated by biological tissues. **Soft and Flexible Structure:** Their physical nature closely mimics natural tissues like skin or mucosa. **Controlled Drug Release:** Hydrogels can deliver medications in a targeted and long-lasting manner. **Stimuli-Responsiveness:** When pH, temperature, or other environmental factors change, smart hydrogels react.

Excellent Permeability: They allow easy diffusion of oxygen, nutrients and waste products.

Ease of Drug Loading: Both hydrophilic and certain lipophilic drugs can be incorporated.

Non-Irritating and Non-Adhesive: They provide a soothing and cooling effect when applied to wounds or skin.

Biodegradability: Many hydrogels can safely degrade within the body after completing their function.

Self-Healing Property (in novel types): Some hydrogels can repair themselves after mechanical damage.

Easy Application: They can be easily applied in the form of patches, gels, or injectable systems.

Mechanical Tunability: Their strength and elasticity can be adjusted by changing polymer concentration or crosslinking.

Support for Cell Growth: Their porous, ECM-like structure supports cell attachment and proliferation in tissue engineering.

Versatile Applications: Used in drug delivery, wound dressings, contact lenses, biosensors, and regenerative medicine.

Hydrogels offer numerous advantages due to their unique three-dimensional polymeric network and high water content, which make them ideal for biomedical and pharmaceutical applications.

They stimulate cell proliferation and tissue regeneration because of their superior biocompatibility and tissue-like qualities, which closely resemble the extracellular matrix. Their ability to provide controlled and sustained drug release, along with responsiveness to stimuli such as pH or temperature, makes them suitable for targeted therapies.

Hydrogels are soft, flexible and comfortable for use in applications like wound dressings and contact lenses. They are also biodegradable, non-toxic and easily modifiable to enhance mechanical strength, adhesion, or functionality. Injectable and self-healing hydrogels further allow minimally invasive delivery

and extended durability. Transparent, permeable and environmentally friendly, hydrogels effectively protect sensitive drugs and ensure efficient nutrient exchange, making them versatile materials for drug delivery, tissue engineering, and regenerative medicine.

DISADVANTAGES OF HYDROGELS [20-24]

Low Mechanical Strength: Hydrogels are often weak and easily damaged under stress or pressure.

Dehydration Sensitivity: Hydrogels can shrink or harden when exposed to dry environments.

Difficult Sterilization: Some hydrogels degrade or lose functionality during heat or radiation sterilization.

Slow Response Time: Stimuli-responsive hydrogels may take time to react to environmental changes.

Complex Manufacturing Process: Preparation often requires careful control of polymerization and cross linking conditions.

Possible Burst Release: Some hydrogels show an initial rapid release of the loaded drug, reducing controlled delivery efficiency.

CLASSIFICATION OF HYDROGELS

Hydrogels can be classified based on different factors and their classification is summed up briefly in Figure 1.

Fig.1:-Classification of Hydrogels

Hydrogel formation involves polymer crosslinking, which may occur through chemical, physical, or combined methods. Various techniques—such as simple mixing, solution casting, bulk or free-radical polymerization, UV or gamma irradiation, and interpenetrating network formation—are commonly used to achieve crosslinking. Additionally, hydrogels can be categorized as cationic, anionic, or neutral hydrogels according to their ionic charge[27]. The charge on the polymer determines the charge on the entire network. Gums, agarose-formed hydrogels, starch, cellulose, glucomannan, pectin, hemicellulose, polysaccharides like alginate, and proteins like collagen and gelatin are examples of natural polymers [28]. Examples of synthetic polymers used to form hydrogels include polyethylene glycol (PEG), polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), polyacrylic acid (PAA), and polyacrylamide (PAM). [29]

Depending on the Synthesis or Composition of Polymers

One type of monomer within the polymeric network makes up the basic structural and functional unit of homopolymer hydrogel. Their skeletons may be cross-linked depending on the type of monomer and the polymerization process. A range of monomeric units containing at least one hydrophilic component are used to create copolymeric hydrogels[30]. Unorganized, block, or alternating configurations are possible for the polymeric network chains. Two distinct, cross-linked components of synthetic or natural polymers bound in a network structure can be used to create a multipolymer interpenetrating polymeric network (IPN). One polymer in semi-interpenetrating hydrogel is cross-linked, whereas the other polymeric component is not. There is no chemical connection when

one straight polymeric chain enters another crosslinked network[31].

Based on Physical and Chemical Composition

- Non-crystalline(Amorphous)
- Semicrystalline, a composite of a morphous and crystalline phases.
- Crystalline.

Based on Cross-Linked Networks:

Physical networks include temporary junctions with entanglements of polymeric chains involving hydrogen bonds, polar or ionic, hydrophobic type of physical contacts, whereas chemically cross-linked networks have permanent bonding involving covalent interaction³².

METHOD OF PREPARATION

Natural, synthetic, and composites of natural and synthetic polymeric materials can all be used to create hydrogels. Hydrogels can be produced by crosslinking polymer chains through methods such as chemical modification, the use of external crosslinkers, high-energy radiation, or graft polymerization. In contrast to physical crosslinking—which relies on non-covalent interactions between polymer chains—chemical crosslinking forms new covalent bonds that permanently link the polymer networks. There are benefits and drawbacks associated with both chemical and physical approaches. Hydrogels with a range of morphologies, sizes, and compositions, including hollow core-shell particles, are produced using conventional and controlled radical polymerization techniques. The most popular method for creating hydrogels is free radical polymerization. In hydrogel synthesis, the gel reactants typically react with a crosslinker in the presence of radical initiators such as ammonium or potassium persulfate to produce three-dimensional crosslinked networks. Hydrogels are produced using a range of physical and

chemical techniques that create a three-dimensional polymer network able to absorb substantial amounts of water or biological fluids. The type of polymer, required qualities, and intended use all influence the process selection. In general, hydrogels can be synthesized from natural or synthetic polymers through cross-linking processes that create a stable network structure. Chemical cross-linking produces hydrogels with great mechanical strength and durability by forming covalent bonds between polymer chains using cross-linking chemicals like formaldehyde, divinylsulfone, or glutaraldehyde. Physical crosslinking, in contrast, yields hydrogels that are generally more biocompatible and reversible because it depends on weaker interactions such as hydrogen bonding, ionic attractions, or hydrophobic interactions. Common physical methods include freezing–thawing, ionic gelation, and complex coacervation, which allow gel formation without the need for chemical initiators or toxic reagents. Another widely used approach is radiation-induced polymerization, where gamma rays or electron beams initiate polymerization and cross-linking without requiring chemical additives, producing pure and sterile hydrogels ideal for biomedical use. Photo polymerization is another modern technique in which UV light activates a photo initiator to cross-link polymer chains under controlled conditions, allowing spatial and temporal control over gel formation, commonly used for in situ or injectable hydrogels. Graft copolymerization is also employed to improve the functional properties of hydrogels by introducing reactive or hydrophilic groups onto existing polymer backbones. Hydrogels with certain particle sizes and swelling capabilities can also be prepared using conventional techniques like emulsion polymerization and solution polymerization. Recently, 3D bioprinting and microfluidic fabrication techniques

have gained attention for producing hydrogels with precise architecture and mechanical properties suitable for tissue engineering and regenerative medicine. Parameters such as polymer concentration, cross-linking density, pH, and temperature play a critical role in determining the gel's porosity, mechanical strength, and swelling behavior. After synthesis, hydrogels are typically washed to remove unreacted monomers or initiators and then dried or hydrated depending on the desired application. Overall, the method of preparation greatly influences the structural integrity, responsiveness, and performance of hydrogels, enabling their use in diverse fields such as drug delivery, wound healing, biosensing and tissue engineering. Free radical polymerization consists of three key stages: initiation, propagation, and termination. During initiation, an initiator breaks apart to form free radicals, which then react with other molecules to generate the first active radical species[33-39]

COMPOSITION OF HYDROGELS [40-44]

Polymer Network: Hydrogels are made from natural polymers, such as chitosan, alginate, and gelatin, or synthetic polymers like polyvinyl alcohol, polyethylene glycol, and polyacrylamide, which form the hydrogel's three-dimensional structure.

Crosslinking Agents: used to provide the hydrogel its strength and elasticity by stabilizing the polymer chains through physical (ionic, hydrogen bonding) or chemical (covalent bonds) interactions.

Aqueous Phase (Water or Biological Fluid): serves as the dispersion medium, giving the hydrogel flexibility and hydration by enabling it to absorb and hold vast volumes of water or biological fluids.

Polyvinyl Alcohol: PVA is a synthetic, water-soluble polymer widely used in hydrogel formulations. It exhibits excellent film-forming, adhesive, and flexible properties. Hydrogels made from PVA show high mechanical strength and biocompatibility. Hydrogels consist of three-dimensional networks formed from either natural polymers, such as chitosan, alginate, and gelatin, or synthetic polymers like polyvinyl alcohol, polyethylene glycol, and polyacrylamide. They are commonly used in wound dressings, contact lenses, and drug delivery applications.

Polyethylene Glycol: PEG is a biocompatible, hydrophilic polymer approved for pharmaceutical use. It enhances the water retention and flexibility of hydrogels. PEG can be combined with other polymers to form biodegradable and non-toxic matrices. It helps in controlled drug release and reducing protein adsorption on surfaces. PEG-based hydrogels are popular in tissue engineering and injectable systems.

Carbopol: Carbopol is a synthetic, high-molecular-weight acrylic acid polymer that swells in water to produce clear, viscous, and stable gels. It offers superior rheological control and increases viscosity. Gelation takes place when neutralized with a base, such as triethanolamine, and it is widely used in ophthalmic, topical, and transdermal hydrogel formulations.

Polyacrylamide: Polyacrylamide is a hydrophilic, water-absorbent polymer. It forms strong, transparent gels suitable for biomedical and analytical uses. Chemically crosslinked PAM hydrogels possess strong mechanical properties and are commonly used in controlled drug delivery and electrophoresis gels. However, the presence of residual

monomers can be toxic, necessitating thorough purification.

Chitosan: Chitosan, a natural polymer derived from chitin found in crustacean shells, is biodegradable, biocompatible, and possesses antibacterial properties. Ionic crosslinking or pH-sensitive gelation are two ways that chitosan creates hydrogels. It supports cell adhesion and wound healing, making it ideal for tissue scaffolds. Extensively used in ocular, nasal, and wound healing hydrogels.

Alginate: Alginate is a natural anionic polysaccharide extracted from brown seaweed that readily forms hydrogels via ionic crosslinking with calcium ions (Ca^{2+}). Alginate gels are biocompatible, non-toxic, and safe for living cells. It has excellent water-holding capacity and tunable porosity. So, it is widely used in wound dressings, drug delivery and tissue engineering.

Gelatin: Collagen is the natural source of the protein gelatin. It creates thermo-reversible hydrogels that melt when heated and gel when cooled. It supports cell growth and tissue regeneration due to its bioactive nature. Gelatin can be chemically crosslinked to improve mechanical stability. Used in biomedical implants, drug delivery and regenerative medicine. Polymeric materials, cross-linking agents, solvents, and additives make up the majority of hydrogels' makeup. These components work together to create a three-dimensional network that can store substantial volumes of water or biological fluids. The polymer component is the backbone of the hydrogel and can be derived from natural sources such as alginate, gelatin, chitosan, agarose, and hyaluronic acid, or from synthetic polymers like polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), polyethylene glycol (PEG), polyacrylamide, and poly(2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate) (HEMA). While synthetic

polymers offer greater mechanical strength and stability, natural polymers offer superior biocompatibility and biodegradability. In order to stabilize the polymer chains and create the network structure, the cross-linking agent is essential. Crosslinking may be chemical, forming covalent bonds using agents like glutaraldehyde or divinyl sulfone, or physical, which depends on weaker interactions such as hydrogen bonds, ionic forces, or hydrophobic interactions. The solvent, usually water or a physiological buffer, acts as a dispersion medium, allowing the hydrogel to swell and maintain its hydrated state. Additives such as plasticizers, stabilizers, or fillers may be incorporated to modify the mechanical, swelling, or degradation properties. Active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) are frequently incorporated into hydrogel matrices for controlled or prolonged release in drug delivery systems.

Additionally, nanoparticles, bioceramics, or biologically active molecules like growth factors can be integrated to enhance bioactivity or functionality. The presence of ionic groups (such as carboxyl, amino, or sulfate) within the polymer chain influences the hydrogel's pH sensitivity and swelling behavior. The ratio of polymer to cross-linker, type of solvent, and degree of cross-linking determine the porosity, elasticity, and water retention capacity of the final product. Hydrogels may also contain initiators or photoinitiators for polymerization reactions, especially in radiation or photochemical methods of preparation. Furthermore, biodegradable linkages can be introduced to ensure safe degradation within the body after fulfilling their function. In some formulations, composite materials like clay or graphene oxide are added to improve mechanical strength or impart conductivity for biosensing applications. Overall, the composition of hydrogels is highly tunable, allowing researchers to design

materials with specific physicochemical, mechanical, and biological properties suited for applications in tissue engineering, wound care, contact lenses and controlled drug delivery systems.

PREPARATION OF HYDROGEL

Ionic gelation, which uses calcium ions as crosslinkers, is a typical method for creating hydrogel. This method involves dissolving sodium alginate (1–4% w/v) in distilled water while stirring constantly until a clear, homogenous solution is achieved. If necessary, the active ingredient or desired medication can be added to this solution. Using a syringe or

pipette, the alginate solution is then gradually added to a calcium chloride (CaCl₂) solution (1–5% w/v). This causes an immediate gel to form as calcium ions take the place of sodium ions in the alginate chains, creating crosslinked calcium alginate networks. The formed hydrogel beads or bulk gels are allowed to stand for 10–30 minutes to complete crosslinking, then washed with distilled water or saline to remove excess calcium ions. The resulting hydrogel is biocompatible, non-toxic, and capable of high water absorption, making it suitable for wound dressings, drug delivery and tissue engineering applications⁴⁵⁻⁴⁷.

Fig.2:-Preparation of Hydrogel

EVALUATION PARAMETERS FOR HYDROGEL [48-51]

Appearance and Homogeneity

The hydrogel should be uniform, smooth and free from lumps or air bubbles. Checked visually for clarity, transparency and color uniformity.

pH Measurement

Measured using a digital pH meter to ensure compatibility with skin or ocular

tissues. The ideal pH range is 5.5–7.4, depending on the application.

Viscosity and Rheological Properties

Determined using a Brookfield viscometer or rheometer. Indicates the flow behavior, spreadability and stability of the hydrogel.

Swelling Index

Evaluated by immersing the hydrogel in buffer and measuring weight gain over time. Reflects the water absorption

capacity and porosity of the hydrogel network.

Gel Strength

Assessed using a texture analyzer to determine firmness, elasticity and compressibility. Important for maintaining structural integrity during application.

Drug Content

Quantified using UV-Vis spectrophotometry or HPLC. Ensures uniform drug distribution and accurate dosage in drug-loaded hydrogels. In Vitro Drug Release Study Performed using Franz diffusion cell or dialysis method. Determines the rate and mechanism of drug release from the hydrogel matrix.

Spreadability

Evaluated by measuring the diameter of gel spread under a known weight. Indicates ease of application and patient compliance.

Bioadhesive Strength

Measured using a texture analyzer or modified balance method. Show how well the hydrogel adheres to biological tissues (skin, mucosa, cornea).

Thermal Analysis

Determines thermal stability, glass transition temperature and polymer crosslinking behavior.

The evaluation of hydrogels involves several physicochemical, mechanical and biological parameters that determine their quality, performance and suitability for pharmaceutical and biomedical applications. Appearance and homogeneity are the primary parameters checked visually to ensure uniformity, absence of air bubbles, and smooth texture. pH assessment is vital to check compatibility with the site of application, as an optimal pH minimizes irritation and ensures drug stability. Viscosity is measured using a viscometer or rheometer to assess the gel's

flow behavior, spreadability, and ease of application. The swelling index, or swelling ratio, is a key property that reflects a hydrogel's capacity to absorb fluids and expand, directly influencing its drug release behavior and bioadhesive performance. Mechanical strength and gel strength are evaluated to determine the elasticity, rigidity and resistance of the hydrogel to deformation, ensuring it maintains structural integrity during use. To guarantee that the active pharmaceutical ingredient is distributed evenly throughout the gel matrix, drug content uniformity is evaluated. In vitro drug release studies are performed to analyze the release kinetics and mechanism of drug diffusion from the hydrogel network, often using diffusion cells or Franz diffusion apparatus. Bioadhesive strength is measured to evaluate the adhesion of the hydrogel to biological tissues, which is essential for mucoadhesive and topical formulations. Thermal analysis using DSC or TGA determines the thermal stability and phase transition behavior of the hydrogel. To verify chemical interactions and effective cross-linking between polymer and medication, Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) is utilized. Additionally, water content and moisture retention are measured to confirm that the hydrogel stays hydrated over extended periods. The stability and longevity of hydrogels in biological contexts can be predicted with the use of degradation studies and biodegradability tests. Sterility and microbial limit tests are performed for hydrogels intended for ophthalmic or injectable applications to ensure safety. Rheological studies provide insights into the gel's viscoelastic behavior and its response to stress or strain. Clarity, spreadability and extrudability are evaluated for patient acceptability and ease of application in topical formulations. Compatibility studies, performed using DSC or FTIR, verify that there are no

interactions between the drug and excipients. In vitro and in vivo biocompatibility tests ensure that the hydrogel does not cause cytotoxicity or inflammation upon application. Stability studies are carried out under different temperature and humidity conditions to evaluate long-term performance. Altogether, these evaluation parameters provide a comprehensive understanding of the hydrogel's physical, chemical, mechanical and biological behavior, ensuring its effectiveness, safety, and reliability for pharmaceutical applications such as controlled drug delivery, wound healing and tissue engineering.

FUTURE ASPECT OF HYDROGEL [51-53]:

Injectable and Self-Healing Hydrogels

The next generation of hydrogels will emphasize injectable and self-healing properties for minimally invasive applications. Injectable hydrogels can be delivered directly to the affected site and solidify in situ under physiological conditions. Self-healing hydrogels can restore their structure after damage, ensuring durability and reusability. Such systems are ideal for tissue engineering, cartilage repair, and localized drug delivery. These features enhance patient comfort, treatment efficiency and long-term functionality. One of the most promising avenues for hydrogel research in the future is injectable and self-healing hydrogels, which provide novel approaches for regenerative medicine, tissue engineering, and controlled drug delivery. These sophisticated hydrogels have the special capacity to be administered as liquid precursors that gel in situ under physiological conditions, enabling accurate localization at the target region and less intrusive delivery. Injectable hydrogels can reduce systemic side effects and improve therapeutic efficacy by encasing medications, growth factors, or living cells and releasing them in a sustained and

regulated manner. They are particularly useful in applications such as localized cancer therapy, wound healing, cartilage repair, and neural regeneration. Self-healing hydrogels, on the other hand, are designed with dynamic and reversible cross-linking mechanisms—such as hydrogen bonding, ionic interactions, host-guest inclusion, or dynamic covalent bonds—that enable them to autonomously repair structural damage and restore their original mechanical properties without external intervention. Their self-healing ability extends their lifespan and makes them suitable for long-term biomedical applications. Combining injectability with self-healing capability offers additional advantages, such as improved adaptability to irregular tissue shapes, reduced surgical intervention, and enhanced durability of implanted materials. Recent research focuses on developing smart injectable and self-healing hydrogels that respond to stimuli like pH, temperature, or enzymes, enabling on-demand drug release or tissue-specific functionality. Furthermore, advancements in nanotechnology and bioengineering have facilitated the design of hydrogels with improved mechanical strength, biocompatibility, and biodegradability. In the future, injectable and self-healing hydrogels are expected to play a crucial role in personalized medicine, 3D bioprinting, and regenerative therapies, bridging the gap between synthetic materials and natural biological tissues to revolutionize modern healthcare.

Hydrogels in Tissue Engineering and Regenerative Medicine

Hydrogels, as biomimetic scaffolds that support cell adhesion, growth, and tissue regeneration, are expected to see ongoing development. They can be designed to replicate the extracellular matrix (ECM) and deliver appropriate mechanical and biological signals. Integration with stem cells and growth factors will promote regeneration of organs and

complex tissues. 3D-printed hydrogel scaffolds will allow customized structures for personalized implants. This will revolutionize wound healing, organ repair and reconstructive medicine.

Nanocomposite and Multifunctional Hydrogels

Hydrogels will use nanomaterials such as nanoparticles, nanotubes, or nanofibers to enhance performance. These nanocomposite hydrogels will have improved mechanical strength, conductivity, and bioactivity. They can serve as biosensors, smart wound dressings, or electro-responsive drug systems. The addition of nanomaterials allows simultaneous drug delivery, sensing, and diagnostic functions. Thus, they represent a bridge between traditional biomaterials and advanced nanomedicine.

APPLICATION OF HYDROGELS

Drug delivery can be achieved using a variety of approaches, formulations, manufacturing processes, preservation procedures, and technology advancements. The medicinal material can be delivered in a variety of ways to achieve the intended medical benefits. Nevertheless, hydrogel is becoming more and more common in regenerative medicine and tissue engineering. The principles of drug delivery include the target-specific site, administration method, drug formulation, optimum efficacy and bioavailability, and enhanced patient comfort and compliance. To alter a drug's pharmacological kinetics and specificity, several hydrogel compositions are employed in drug administration. Hydrogels have gained significant importance in the pharmaceutical field due to their unique structural, physicochemical, and biological characteristics that make them suitable for a wide variety of drug delivery and therapeutic applications. Their high water absorption capacity, biocompatibility and soft tissue-like nature make them effective

carriers for both hydrophilic and hydrophobic drugs. In controlled and sustained drug delivery, hydrogels provide gradual and prolonged release of therapeutic agents by regulating diffusion and swelling, thus maintaining optimal drug concentration at the target site for an extended duration. This minimizes dosing frequency and enhances patient compliance. Stimuli-responsive hydrogels, also known as smart hydrogels, respond to environmental changes such as pH, temperature, or ionic strength, enabling site-specific and on-demand drug release. For example, pH-sensitive hydrogels can release drugs selectively in the stomach or intestine, depending on local conditions. In topical and transdermal formulations, hydrogels are widely used for delivering drugs through the skin due to their cooling effect, non-greasy nature, and ease of application. They provide a soothing base for dermatological preparations and are used for anti-inflammatory, antifungal, and analgesic medications. Hydrogels have also demonstrated great promise in the field of ophthalmic medication administration; they are utilized in contact lenses and in situ-forming gels to extend ocular residence time and enhance drug bioavailability. In oral drug delivery, hydrogels can encapsulate sensitive drugs like proteins, peptides, or enzymes, protecting them from the acidic environment of the stomach and ensuring controlled release in the intestine.

Hydrogels are also widely utilized in wound dressings, where they maintain a moist environment conducive to healing, absorb exudates, provide cooling relief, and prevent infection. Their transparency allows easy observation of the wound without removal of the dressing. Injectable hydrogels have transformed localized drug delivery by forming gels directly at the site of administration, allowing for minimally invasive treatment of cancer, inflammation, and chronic pain. These hydrogels can deliver therapeutic agents

directly to the target tissue, reducing systemic side effects. In tissue engineering and regenerative medicine, hydrogels serve as scaffolds that mimic the extracellular matrix, promoting cell attachment, proliferation, and differentiation, thus aiding in the regeneration of tissues such as skin, cartilage and bone.

Furthermore, hydrogels play a vital role in protein and peptide delivery, as they can maintain the biological activity of fragile biomolecules while releasing them in a controlled manner. In gene delivery, specially engineered hydrogels can encapsulate DNA or RNA and release them under specific physiological conditions, enabling targeted gene therapy. Mucoadhesive hydrogels enhance drug retention at mucosal sites like the buccal, nasal, vaginal, or rectal membranes, improving absorption and therapeutic effectiveness. Nanocomposite hydrogels, which incorporate nanoparticles, offer multifunctional benefits such as improved mechanical strength, responsiveness, and even imaging capability for theranostic applications.

Hydrogels are also employed in dental applications for the long-term release of fluoride or antiseptics, as well as in oral care formulations like mouth gels. They are also employed in implantable drug delivery systems, where they can release anticancer agents or hormones over extended periods. Bioadhesive hydrogels improve the residence time of formulations at the site of application, enhancing localized treatment efficiency.

Compared to traditional eye drops, hydrogel-based methods in ocular medicine, such as drug-loaded contact lenses, guarantee longer residence times and improved bioavailability. In nasal drug delivery, hydrogels provide mucoadhesion and protect drugs from rapid clearance, allowing systemic absorption of peptides and proteins. Their application extends to biosensors and diagnostic devices, where

hydrogels act as immobilization matrices for enzymes and antibodies due to their porous and hydrated nature. Moreover, hydrogels are employed in 3D bioprinting to create drug-releasing scaffolds and customized medical implants. Their combination of controlled drug release, biocompatibility, mechanical flexibility, and ease of use makes hydrogels a highly versatile and promising material in pharmaceutical applications. Their adaptability allows formulation scientists to tailor drug release profiles and target specific tissues or organs, thereby improving therapeutic outcomes. As research continues, the integration of nanotechnology, smart polymers, and bioresponsive systems is expected to expand the scope of hydrogels in personalized medicine, advanced drug delivery systems, and regenerative healthcare applications. The variety of tenability of the hydrogels has delivered drugs in controlled and sustained manners. The rise in the worldwide incidence of infectious and chronic diseases is another factor that might have impacted the development of advanced drug delivery systems. Hydrogels can effectively facilitate the pharmacological actions, drug kinetics, and therapeutic effects of various drug delivery systems.⁵⁴

Targeted drug delivery

Hydrogel has been used in targeted drug delivery loaded with therapeutic agent at a particular site without affecting neighbouring tissues under different stimulating factors, including pH and temperature. Interest in this field has increased because of the potential advantages of tailored pharmaceutical administration in treating chronic illnesses, cancer, and other conditions. The highly developed drug-targeted system must get past the host tissue's defences and reach the predicted action spot to achieve the desired targeted effect. Tissue engineering has investigated novel nanotechnology,

including nano hydrogels and nanogels, for drug delivery to specific tissues to address medical problems. Targeted drug delivery using hydrogels is an emerging and highly promising area in pharmaceutical research aimed at improving therapeutic efficiency while minimizing side effects. Hydrogels serve as ideal carriers for targeted delivery because of their high water content, tunable porosity, biocompatibility and ability to encapsulate a wide range of drugs, including small molecules, proteins, and nucleic acids. Through passive or active targeting mechanisms, they can be designed to deliver medications precisely to the sick spot. Hydrogels use physiological changes between healthy and diseased tissues, such as pH, temperature, or enzyme levels, to induce drug release at the targeted site in passive targeting. Active targeting involves the incorporation of ligands, antibodies, or peptides on the hydrogel surface that recognize and bind to specific receptors expressed on target cells, such as cancer or inflamed tissues. This approach allows precise localization of therapeutic agents, reducing systemic exposure and improving treatment outcomes. Moreover, stimuli-responsive hydrogels can be designed to release drugs in response to internal stimuli like pH or redox potential, or external triggers such as light, magnetic fields, or temperature changes, ensuring controlled and site-specific release. Targeted hydrogel systems are especially useful in cancer therapy, ocular drug delivery, wound healing, and brain disorders, where localized treatment is essential. For instance, pH-sensitive hydrogels release anticancer drugs preferentially in the acidic microenvironment of tumors, while temperature-sensitive ones are effective for thermo responsive delivery. Advances in nano composite and injectable hydrogel technology have further enhanced targeting precision by allowing the

incorporation of nanoparticles, liposomes, or micelles for dual delivery and imaging purposes. In the future, the integration of smart, biodegradable, and multifunctional hydrogels will revolutionize targeted drug delivery, offering personalized, safe, and efficient therapeutic solutions tailored to individual patient needs.

Controlled drug delivery

The multifunctional behaviour of the hydrogels is due to a variety of functional groups, and these may interact with therapeutic agents for their sustained release. The drug delivery method can release therapeutic compounds with clinical benefits, despite the limited bioavailability and plasma levels of conventional drug delivery systems. Therapeutic chemicals that could not be effective without a dependable delivery system are released over an extended period of time by the firmly crosslinked hydrogels. To ensure maximum efficacy and safety, the drug needs to be delivered to the target tissue at a regulated rate. Creating hydrogels capable of controlled drug release addresses the limitations of conventional drug administration methods. Microspheres of carboxymethyl chitosan were prepared and incorporated into a polymeric matrix composed of hyaluronic acid and gelatin hydrogels, enabling controlled drug delivery for the treatment of inflammatory bowel diseases. They have reported that the formulation has sustained the release of curcumin in vitro, and pharmacodynamic studies have shown that hydrogel-loaded curcumin has excellent therapeutic approaches to colitis in mice models. Because of their high water content and biocompatibility, hydrogels are frequently used as prolonged and regulated drug delivery methods. Both hydrophilic and hydrophobic medications can be encapsulated by them and released under regulated conditions. Drug distribution that is site-specific based on pH, temperature, or enzyme activity is

made possible by their stimuli-responsive nature. Hydrogels create a wet environment that speeds up tissue regeneration and wound healing. They offer cooling, soothing, and non-adhesive properties, reducing pain during dressing changes. Many hydrogel dressings also incorporate antimicrobial or anti-inflammatory agents for enhanced healing.

Ophthalmic and Contact Lens Applications

Hydrogels are usually used in soft contact lenses due to their high oxygen permeability and flexibility. They can also serve as transporters for ocular drug delivery, ensuring prolonged contact with the corneal surface. Their transparency and biocompatibility make them safe and comfortable for eye-related applications.

CONCLUSION

Large volumes of water or biological fluids can be absorbed and retained by hydrogels, which are three-dimensional, hydrophilic polymeric networks. They are ideal for a wide range of biomedical and pharmaceutical applications due to their special softness, flexibility, and biocompatibility. Physical or chemical crosslinking techniques can be used to create hydrogels from synthetic or natural polymers, each of which affects the hydrogels' structure and characteristics. Due to their tissue-like consistency, hydrogels closely mimic the extracellular matrix (ECM) and provide an excellent environment for cell growth and tissue regeneration. They are widely used in drug delivery, wound healing, contact lenses, and tissue engineering. The therapeutic potential of advanced hydrogels has been further increased by the development of stimuli-responsive, self-healing, and injectable varieties. But there are still issues like low mechanical strength, dehydration, and poor stability. Ongoing research aims to overcome these limitations by developing nanocomposite,

biodegradable, and smart hydrogels with enhanced functionality. In the future, hydrogels are expected to play a crucial role in personalized medicine, regenerative therapy, and advanced biomedical devices. In summary, hydrogels are an inventive, safe, and adaptable platform that has the potential to completely transform therapeutic delivery systems, healthcare and diagnostics.

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